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JOURNAL OF HEPATO-GASTROENTEROLOGY RESEARCH

ЖУРНАЛ ГЕПАТО-ГАСТРОЭНТЕРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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EFFECTIVENESS OF USE OF THE DRUG MONTELUKAST FOR BRONCHIAL ASTHMA IN CHILDREN

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ANNOTATION

Bronchial asthma is a disease manifested by reversible bronchial obstruction, the pathogenetic basis of which is allergic inflammation of the airways and, in most cases, bronchial hyperreactivity [1,2,3]. Early adequate initiation of treatment with anti-inflammatory drugs helps reduce inflammatory changes, reduce the severity of the disease and the risk of exacerbations, and improve the quality of life of children. Purpose of the study: to study the effectiveness of Montelukast in bronchial asthma in children. Materials and methods of research. There were 30 boys, 18 girls. The children's ages ranged from 3 to 14 years. Conclusions. The use of Montelukast indicates its effectiveness as a drug for long-term control of bronchial asthma in children. Montelukast reduces the symptoms of bronchial asthma, improves pulmonary function, and reduces the risk of exacerbation. Montelukast is well tolerated and is an easy-to-use drug for basic therapy of bronchial asthma.

Key words: bronchial asthma, antileukotrienes, montelukast, treatment, children

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ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ПРЕПАРАТА МОНТЕЛУКАСТ ПРИ БРОНХИАЛЬНОЙ АСТМЕ У ДЕТЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Бронхиальная астма представляет собой заболевание, проявляющееся обратимой обструкцией бронхов, патогенетическую основу которого составляют аллергическое воспаление дыхательных путей и, в большинстве случаев, гиперреактивность бронхов [1,2,3]. Раннее адекватное начало лечения с применением противовоспалительных препаратов способствует уменьшению воспалительных изменений, снижению тяжести заболевания и риска развития обострений, улучшению качества жизни детей. Цель исследования: изучить эффективность монтелукаста при бронхиальной астме у детей. Материалы и методы исследования. Мальчиков было 30, девочек 18. Возраст детей колебался от 3 до 14 лет. Выводы. Применение Монтелукаста указывает на его эффективность как препарата для длительного контроля бронхиальной астмы у детей. Монтелукаст уменьшает симптомы бронхиальной астмы, улучшает функцию легких, снижает риск обострения. Монтелукаст хорошо переносится и является простым в применении препаратом базисной терапии бронхиальной астмы.

Ключевые слова: бронхиальная астма, антилейкотриены, монтелукаст, лечение, дети

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BOLALARDA BRONXIAL ASTMAGA MONTELUKAST DORINI QO'LLANISH SAMARALI

ANNOTATSIYA

Bronxial astma - qaytariladigan bronxial obstruksiya bilan namoyon bo'ladigan kasallik bo'lib, uning patogenetik asosini nafas yo'llarining

allergik yallig'lanishi va ko'p hollarda bronxial giperreaktivlik tashkil qiladi [1,2,3]. Yallig'lanishga qarshi dorilar bilan davolanishni erda boshlash yallig'lanish o'zgarishlarini kamaytirishga, kasallikning og'irligini va kuchayish xavfini kamaytirishga va bolalarning hayot sifatini yaxshilashga yordam beradi. Tadqiqot maqsadi: bolalarda bronxial astmada Montelukastning samaradorligini o'rganish. Tadqiqot materiallari va usullari. 30 o'g'il, 18 qiz. Bolalarning yoshi 3 yoshdan 14 yoshgacha bo'lgan. Xulosa. Montelukastdan foydalanish bolalarda bronxial astmani uzoq muddatli nazorat qilish uchun preparat sifatida uning samaradorligini ko'rsatadi. Montelukast bronxial astma belgilarini kamaytiradi, o'pka faoliyatini yaxshilaydi va kuchayishi xavfini kamaytiradi. Montelukast yaxshi muhosa qilinadi va bronxial astmaning asosiy terapiyasi uchun foydalanish uchun qulay doridir.

Kalit so'zlar: bronxial astma, antileykotrienlar, montelukast, davolash, bolalar

Relevance. Recently, throughout the world there has been an increase in the prevalence of allergic diseases in children and, in particular, bronchial asthma. In this regard, the study of development mechanisms, principles of diagnosis and rational methods of treatment, knowledge of the principles of emergency care is of particular importance and relevance. [12,14,16]. An attack of bronchial asthma can pose an immediate threat to the life of a child, so a doctor of any specialty must be able to provide emergency care in these cases. [5,8,9,11]. Allergic diseases and especially bronchial asthma, occurring in childhood, can lead to disability of the child. Therefore, knowledge of methods of prevention and rehabilitation of this disease is of great social importance. Obstructive airway diseases are often severe and can lead to acute respiratory failure [6,12,13,17]. In this regard, knowledge of the clinic, diagnosis, emergency treatment of acute respiratory failure is necessary for a doctor of any profile. The problem of rational treatment is one of the most pressing problems in pediatrics [4,7,10,15]

In pediatric practice, the main route of drug administration should be oral, since it is the least traumatic.

Purpose of the study: to study the effectiveness of Montelukast in bronchial asthma in children

Materials and methods of research. In the children's department of the Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Care and the pulmonology department of the regional children's multidisciplinary center, 48 sick children with bronchial asthma were treated. The diagnosis was established on the basis of anamnestic data, clinical data, instrumental and laboratory data. There were 30 boys, 18 girls. The children's ages ranged from 3 to 14 years.

Sick children were divided into three groups: the first group of 16 children received montelukast. In group 2 there were 16 children who received inhaled glucocorticosteroids. In group 3 there were 16 children who received sodium cromoglycate.

Analysis of anamnestic data in the examined children showed that pathology of the perinatal period and childbirth was observed in 40.5% of patients. 54.5% of children were on early artificial feeding. A family history of allergic pathology was identified in 61.8% of patients: maternal gender – 64%, paternal gender – 36%. The patients also had relatives with asthma. Among the concomitant diseases in sick children, frequent diseases of the ENT organs were recorded: adenoiditis - in 40% of children, chronic tonsillitis - in 16%, which led to frequent ARI in 75% of children. At the beginning of the study, all patients had symptoms of bronchial asthma more than once a week.

Children of the main groups received Montelukast orally in the form of a chewable tablet once a day at night in a dose of 4 mg for children from 3 to 6 years old and 5 mg for children from 6 to 14 years old. The comparison groups were treated with inhaled glucocorticosteroids. The duration of the course of therapy was 6 months.

Results and discussions. The results of the treatment showed positive dynamics in the manifestations of bronchial asthma in all children, which was manifested by a decrease in the frequency of asthma attacks and the need for short-acting bronchodilators, and improved well-being.

During therapy with montelukast, positive dynamics of clinical manifestations were noted already in the first week of treatment in 30 (62.5%) patients, and were more pronounced at the end of the first month of drug therapy.

A significant decrease in the number of asthma attacks occurred at 4-5 weeks of therapy. The average frequency of nocturnal asthma attacks before treatment was 2.8, and after four weeks of therapy these symptoms were not observed.

The number of asthma episodes under treatment with the drug decreased by 2.3 times the night symptoms of the disease; The need for bronchodilators decreased by 6 times, the number of asymptomatic days increased by 1.4. In sick children treated with montelukast in the third month of therapy, almost no nocturnal attacks of suffocation were observed, and in children receiving inhaled glucocorticosteroids, nocturnal episodes of the disease occurred rarely.

All children noted the simplicity and convenience of using montelukast compared to inhaled glucocorticosteroids, and the children liked the drug's taste. As can be seen from the results of examination and treatment of bronchial asthma in children, the use of Montelukast was accompanied by rapid positive dynamics; asthma attacks in sick children decreased already in the first week of treatment, and were more pronounced at the end of the first month of drug therapy.

During the study period, no adverse reactions were observed with montelukast therapy. Children tolerated montelukast well.

Conclusions. The use of Montelukast indicates its effectiveness as a drug for long-term control of bronchial asthma in children. Montelukast reduces the symptoms of bronchial asthma, improves pulmonary function, and reduces the risk of exacerbation. Montelukast is well tolerated and is an easy-to-use drug for basic therapy of bronchial asthma.

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